

Content Essence and Analysis of Teacher Training for Innovation Activities

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Abstract

This article discusses the system of professional competence development of science teachers in schools and its role and advantages in life. Forms of professional competence of teachers are also mentioned.

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Introduction

World experience shows that in the organization of professional development of pedagogical personnel, the development of a data-based system of professional development is considered as the main directions aimed at independent professional development by ensuring its continuity and mastering modern educational technologies and new forms of professional development. Professional development of young or experienced scientific and pedagogical personnel in England is organized on the basis of different approaches. In the US, monitoring of the qualification of teachers is carried out through the automated management system of the Federal Ministry of Education. Teachers also allocate 30 percent of their working time to practice-oriented activities. This activity ensures that the educator will increase his competence in practice and will be in constant contact with the current processes associated with his specialty in the labor market.

Main part

In the processes of retraining and professional development of pedagogical personnel, the development of professional training of the audience at the level of modern requirements, the formation of the necessary knowledge, skills and skills in them with the effective use of modern pedagogical and information and Communication Technologies is one of the important tasks. After all, now the quality of the qualification process is associated with the rapid implementation of modern information and communication technologies into practice.

Studying the experiences of the developed countries of the world, taking into account local conditions, economic and social resources, the implementation of radical reforms in all spheres of society's life has been ensuring the achievement of new achievements. Although the international cooperation in various fields is yielding its results, however, it requires individual dedication, dedication, enthusiasm and determination from members of the society to strengthen national independence in all respects, enrichment of achievements, rapid elimination of existing shortcomings.

Teachers who work in the same way as teachers of the above-mentioned requirements possess the first experience on the use of interactive methods, pedagogical and information and communication technologies in teaching in the case of harmonic. We can also see that each educator has also developed an innovative competence.

It is known that innovation is a theoretical, maxed-out and practical innovation. Any innovation, added innovation, requires a high level of emotionality and resourcefulness from the educated. For these reasons, innovations in education are gradually opening the way to itself. When we observe the process of growing up in secondary schools and higher educational institutions, Innovation Practice requires not only to engage in active dialogue with the teacher, but also to be active and initiative in understanding the world.

Today, we see not only the innovation system of education, but also the activity of the psyche of educators. The concept of "innovative education" is interpreted differently in the scientific literature: when a number of authors look at innovations from a philosophical and theoretical point of view, others understand some factor in the educational process, for example, active methods of education, or technical means of Education, rational use. The essence of educational innovations in their practical nature: they are aimed at shaping the dignity of graduates of higher education, as well as innovation in the audience of professional development courses. Therefore, when we say innovations in higher education, we understand the innovative enthusiasm of developing new knowledge and education. A. when innovation says enthusiasm. K. Markova understands that the transformation of new knowledge into technological or social reality, the transformation of scientific knowledge into

a sphere of commodity or service. A characteristic feature of innovative education is self-administration, professionalism, centrality (anropocentrism). The objectives of innovative education are as follows: to ensure a high level of spiritual and personal development of Education recipients; to create conditions for the acquisition of skills of scientific thinking of Education recipients; to teach the methodology of introducing innovations in socio-economic and professional spheres.

Many educators understand professionalism as follows: the level of skill in finding a solution to professional issues; the ability to conduct their professional activities; intellect personal level of development; availability of basic qualifications and competency. So it turns out that the professional competence of each educator is also important.

In a number of studies, the professional competence inherent directly to the educator and its peculiarities have been studied. Among such studies. This means that innovation is a process of education (professional culture), which allows him to master the means of understanding professional issues and methods of solution in the manner of movement of social and universal knowledge and skills towards technologies.

Professional competence of pedagogue in Uzbekistan, its peculiarities have been studied and among them. The study conducted by Nazarova plays a special role. According to the researcher, on the basis of professional competence inherent in pedagogy, the following are the structural bases. Having professional and pedagogical competence, it is important to work on oneself, self-development. Self-development tasks are determined by self-analysis and self-assessment.

The system of continuing education, in particular, introduced to secondary schools in general, follows the process of competency-related education and training:

- * Technological innovation-the purposeful use of information and communication technologies in the educational process based on the competency approach;

- * Pedagogical innovations-require the introduction of innovations such as the renewal of the educational process on the basis of a compensatory approach, its progress and the use of technologies at the local and private methodological level that enable the cognitive activity of students;

It is known that the introduction of the above-mentioned innovations into the educational process requires a certain methodical knowledge, skills and qualifications from the teacher, as well as pedagogical competence(merit).

The teacher's acquisition of modern methodical knowledge, skills and skills, as well as the availability of pedagogical competence(merit)will be the basis for his / her presumption of the adult education of a competent person in his / her pedagogical activity.

What kind of knowledge does the innovative learning environment, which is based on the competency approach, require from the teachers? In particular, it should be noted that the changes introduced into the professional and pedagogical training of the teacher as a result of the creation of an innovative educational environment included in the teaching process remain unnoticed.

As a proof of our opinion, the development of professional and personal competence of teachers of secondary schools in general can be called a subconscious, which does not imply a complex (pedagogical, psychological and methodical) analysis of the characteristics of each educational subject, components of the teacher's professional and pedagogical training and pedagogical competence (merit), as well as lessons conducted by teachers.and this hinders the good assimilation of some aspects of education from our teachers.

The low level of professional motivation of teachers, the lack of purposeful research on the increase of their professional and pedagogical training, as a result of the lack of complex side-effects to the pedagogical activity of the teacher, lead to the organization of the educational process in the form of templates.

Based on the above points, there was a need for teachers to clarify their pedagogical competence (merit).

Pedagogical competence (merit) is a professional and psychological feature of the teacher, which is the sum of the qualities that characterize the practical and theoretical action of subjective conditions in the organization and management of pedagogical activity.

Teachers' competences are divided into two groups:

1. Basic competences of the teacher;
2. Teacher's private competences;

In didactic literature, materials on the types of pedagogical competence (competence) of the teacher were analyzed, and appropriate changes were made to it, taking into account the requirements of the innovative educational environment, which are brought into the body on the basis of a compensatory approach.

It should be noted that the basic competency of teachers of Science in secondary schools is common for pedagogical personnel engaged in pedagogical activity in these educational institutions.

The teacher's private competences differ in the content of the educational process organized by this teacher in science and its role in the perfection of a competent person.

The basic competency of science teachers in secondary schools serves as the basis for the formation of the teacher's private competences in them.

The above two types of pedagogical competences are closely connected with each other and are subject to each other. Therefore, a complex approach to the process of formation of these compensations is required.

In this regard, it should be noted that each educator is required to carry out the following in the process of professional development:

- the model of development of competence of preparation of teachers for innovative activities in the process of professional development on the basis of objective, motivation, clarification of the content of technological, reflexive components aimed at increasing positive motivation in the audience;
- determination of teachers in the process of professional development on the basis of factors that directly and indirectly affect the content, structure, levels of competency in preparation for innovative activities;
- creation of multimedia information and educational resources aimed at assessing the competence and determining the levels of preparation of teachers for innovative activities
- development of recommendations for improvement of pedagogical opportunities for the development of competence of preparation of teachers for innovative activities in the process of professional development.

The above-mentioned compensations serve as one of the main features of each of these educators today.

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Thus, the need to withstand the strong competition that occurs in the labor market in the conditions of market relations motivates each Specialist to find in himself a composition of professional competence and qualities inherent in it.

The innovation competence of the educator is also important. Today, it is necessary for every educator to focus on self-consistent development to have professional competence. This, in turn, can clearly and unbiased characterize the qualities of competency that exist in pedagogues and the quality, knowledge, skills and skills that need to be developed.

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